

What You Need to Know About Duqu 2.0

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2015 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150612> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Media [1] *report* [2] that Russian security company *Kaspersky* [3] has been compromised during an electronic break-in. The incident, the malware used by the attackers and the political context of the attack have led to an increased media interest and questions to scip AG regarding the attack *Kaspersky* has dubbed *Duqu 2.0*.

The following should give you an overview over the most important aspects of the case.

3. What Happened?

Russian security research company *Kaspersky reported* [4] on June 10th, 2015, that they have fallen victim to an attack. Eugene Kaspersky, founder of the company, describes how researchers discovered the attack, how it has been analysed and what conclusions they can draw.

4. Which Malware was Used?

A first analysis by *Kaspersky* has shown that malware was used that is identical with the malware known as *Duqu* [5] in key aspects. Therefore the Malware was named *Duqu 2.0* by the researchers. The first version of *Duqu* was used during attacks in 2011.

5. What Makes Duqu 2.0 Remarkable?

An extended analysis by security company *Symantec* has shown that the extended version *Duqu 2.0* mainly has three new features:

1. There is *more functionality* in *Duqu 2.0*
2. The Malware is almost entirely contained to RAM of an infected system. This makes a forensic analysis difficult, as *very little to no data is stored persistently*.

3. The installed basis acts as a *Botnet* and can be controlled centrally using Command-and-Control servers. Therefore, infected systems can be *remote controlled*.

6. Why was Kaspersky Attacked?

Security companies are lucrative targets for a variety of attackers. Manufacturers such as *Kaspersky* research and develop new technologies combatting computer attacks and malware. If an attacker gains access to the security company's research, the attacker holds a *strategic* and *tactical advantage* for further attacks.

7. How Were Other Victims Identified?

There are two possibilities to identify victims of malware:

1. Modern anti virus solutions allow reporting of identified malware, giving manufacturers a statistical overview over infected systems
2. Analysing Command-and-Control servers that remote control infected systems, researchers can identify further activity by the attacker. To do this, however, researchers need access to communication originating from the command-and-control server. Sometimes, compromising and forensic analysis of the command and control server is necessary. If that has happened in the case of *Duqu 2.0* is debated.

8. Who is behind Duqu 2.0?

Kaspersky emphasises that they can not *conclusively* name a culprit. The complexity and professionalism of *Duqu* and *Duqu 2.0* point to an attacker with considerable financial means. The most likely culprits based on this are *governments* and *organised crime*. The targets have primarily been *political* in nature. This points to the attacker being a *governmental agency*. Among the targets were political talks regarding *Iran's nuclear weapons program* or celebrations of the *70th Anniversary of the Liberation of Auschwitz-Birkenau*. These are all indicators that *Duqu 2.0* is an *Israeli* product. This assessment remains unconfirmed.

9. External Links

[1] <http://www.computerworld.com/article/2934398/cybercrime-hacking/duqu-20-hackers-may-have-cracked-kaspersky-to-recon-research.html>
[2] <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2015/jun/11/duqu-20-computer-virus-with-traces-of-israeli-code-was->

[used-to-hack-iran-talks](#)

[3] <http://www.kaspersky.com>

[4] <https://blog.kaspersky.com/kaspersky-statement-duqu-attack/>

[5] <https://securelist.com/blog/incidents/31177/the-mystery-of-duqu-part-one-5/>